

Recommended citation: Neto, C., & Bernardino, J. (2017). A Parallel Between Android and iOS Design Guidelines . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 833-838). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698279.

A Parallel Between Android and iOS Design Guidelines

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ABSTRACT

The proliferation of smartphones and the user centric design philosophy behind it makes interaction and user experience a key piece when designing mobile applications. This paper is a side-by-side analogy and comparison of design guidelines for both Android and iOS platforms. The comparison include navigation, screen size, interaction and motion, colour and backwards compatibility. This work will help students to set some of the foundations required to establish models or tools for designing user interfaces for platform convergent solutions.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills; Curriculum Development

Keywords: Android, iOS, Material Design, Human Interface Guidelines

1 INTRODUCTION

Interaction and user experience are currently the main key factors for the success of an application. On the other hand, there is a worldwide market of 3,4 billion devices [1], used for a wide range of tasks from browsing the web, gaming, shopping and use services. As such, developers and designers are required to provide a match and fluid experience across devices and platforms that have audiences with a distinct culture and principles but with the same goals [2].

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Material Design and iOS Human Interface Guidelines [1] [3] exist to provide consistency and continuity, granting third party applications look and behaviour, allowing seamless integration with the operating system.

In this paper we compare design guidelines under the scope criteria concerning device resolution, navigation, interaction and interface components, in order to establish similarities between Android and iOS application design wise.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the evolution of smartphone interaction and user experience. Section 3 gives the main principles of mobile interface guidelines. Section 4 establishes a comparison of key points for application design and development, comprising screen size and resolution, navigation, colour schemas, usage and backwards compatibility. Finally, Section 5 presents our main conclusions and suggests some future work.

2 EVOLUTION OF SMARTPHONE INTERACTION AND USER EXPERIENCE

Launched in 2007 the first generation Apple iPhone changed the industry deeply concerning user interface and experience given that interaction was touch based without a stylus. For the first time users were prompted to touch elements on the screen aided by the familiarity of UI elements that mimic real life materials as such as metal, paper, wood or glass. Also the iPhone set apart from major competitors as it had only one main button to interact with the devices, contrary to others with physical keyboards like RIM Blackberry, or models sporting Symbian the mobile dominant OS due the need of a stylus. Until 2010 no platform would present a design language that would shape the interface and experience across multiple type of devices, and Microsoft brought that with Windows Phone and the Metro Design language (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Windows Phone 7

A design language is used to provide a consistent and unique look and feel as it lays out approaches and choices for design elements like colour, shapes, textures materials and others. With that purpose on Windows Phone 7, Metro Design Language opted for typography in favour of an iconographic User interface, as in Android and iOS, focusing more on content and less on the decorations, a trait that later design languages inherited.

This minimalism trend helped cement that users no longer required reality approached metaphors to interact with the system, and in a way it influenced Apple iOS 7 identities. When announced in September 2013, the iOS 7 had its elements revised, to remove lustrous decorations and its skeuomorphic elements it also introduced a deep revision of the Human Interface Guidelines itself.

3 MOBILE INTERFACE GUIDELINES

A design language is used to provide a consistent and unique look and feel, as it lays out approaches and choices for design elements like colour, shapes, textures materials and others. In next sections, iOS and Android interface guidelines are briefly described.

3.1 iOS Human Interface Guidelines

Human Interface Guidelines (HIG) is the iOS specification for building user interfaces that also serves as basis for Apple evaluation process when apps are submitted to the App Store [1].

HIG promotes the principles of deference, referring that the User Interface (UI) must never outshine the application content. This is emphasized by the translucence and blurring of elements which helps to focus on content without distracting the user. Clarity is the second principle to set apart the most important content and interaction. This is enforced by the use of colour for elements state change, and a clean typography with the sans serif Font San Francisco SF. The use of depth with blurring and translucence is the final principle enforced by HIG, helping to separate the content.

The guidelines were redesigned on iOS7, where a grid system was put in place redefining the space between elements and the fonts where made bigger. Finally, colour was introduced as a main state change to communicate with the user, ending the skeuomorphism omnipresent on prior versions of iOS (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2. iOS App Anatomy

3.2 Google Material Design

Google's Material Design is a design language introduced as visual guideline for Android 5.0 aka Lollipop [3]. It was conceived to provide design guidelines for applications that run on a wide array of devices including smartphones, tablets and personal computers. The language is a metaphor for a dynamic transformable material akin to paper that uses elevation to differentiate on hierarchy, bold colour for identity and motion and animation for feedback. It encourages the use of white space and establishes a metric relationship of elements by the adoption of a grid-based system to layout UI elements [3].

Another principle of Material Design it's the principle of motion with meaning, expressed through the use of animation in a denominated UI choreography, keeping a coordinated behaviour in transitioning elements when using path based animations

and transitions. Material Design is also a language that is in constant evolution it's not a static concept as Metro, the guidelines are updated with new elements and definitions while other existing concepts are refined.

4 CONNECTING GUIDELINES

Rather than learning, developers and designers tend to introduce foreign elements to the platform. It is not uncommon to see applications on Android with iOS elements. This may be traced to company policies, user demands, trends and other factors that affect the design process of smartphone application [7-10].

On the following sections, key points to help with a convergent and consistent application design will be observed. Each section was based on a suggested approach by Google Design advocate Roman Nurik for iOS designers entering the Android design [4].

4.1 Interaction and Motion

Human Interface Guidelines (HIG) is the iOS specification for building user interfaces that also serves as basis for Apple evaluation process when apps are submitted to the App Store [1].

4.2 Screen sizes and Resolution

Mobile applications are expected to be responsive and adapt to screen density, size and device type. Both platforms implement a scale independent unit of measure that allows elements to be measured on screen and work the same way dp (density pixels) for Android and points on iOS. By providing scale and resolution independent specifications on both platforms, designers allow developers to easily implement screens since the operative system scales accordingly to the measures provided.

4.3 Navigation

Android has physical buttons that affect navigation and application states. This buttons can currently be physical on the device or emulated on screen. The back button is the one that makes the key difference here since it is omnipresent and influential to the app state changes. On iOS there is only one physical button that when pressed may put the application to a halt state and/or sent to background.

4.4 Colour

On Material Design app it is recommended to limit the applications palette to at least three colours: the primary, a darker tone of the primary, and another colour that must be complementary to the other two primary colours. HIG states that colour improves communication, and on platform it helps to indicate interactive elements and provide continuity. It also recommends to consider colour blindness by avoiding using red and green for state changes, to stick with a key colour for interactivity and state changes, and warns for cultural differences between countries and how colour should be used as communication vehicle [4].

4.5 Backwards Compatibility

Android ensures backwards compatibility with the Support Library, which allows keeping appearance and functionality back to version 2.1, reducing the impact posed by fragmentation [5].

Due to the fast rate of adoption of new versions and the way Apple pushes updates, developers may opt to drop support of previous versions of iOS with little to no

impact to the application. Depending on logic and features implemented, there might be the need to alter or provide different or extra logic to support those versions.

4.6 Component Similarity

When designing an application, basic interface components are used to represent and interact with information. These blocks, buttons, tables or menus depend on the numerous use cases given our application requirements. Table 1 represents a comparison between each component, stating the analogous of an Android screen on iOS and vice versa based on work by other authors [6] and guideline documentation.

Table 1. Components with similar usage scenarios

Android	iOS
ViewGroup	UIView
TextView	UILabel
EditText	UITextField, UITextView
Button	UIButton
ImageView	UIImageView
RecyclerView	UICollectionView
ViewPager	UIPageControl
Listview, RecyclerView	UITableView
TabLayout, Tab	UITabBar, UITabBarItem
Toolbar	UINavigationController
AlertDialogBox	AlertView
DialogFragment	UIPopoverController
Slider	UISlider
Switch, Checkbox, ToggleButton	UISwitch
ProgressBar	UIActivityIndicatorView
Popup Menu	Action Sheet
Option Menu, Action Items	UIBarButtonItem
Spinner	UIPickerView
WebView	UIWebView
ScrollView	UIScrollView
Intents	App Extensions

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The main objective of this paper was to show the similarities of the design guidelines and application components between Android and iOS, as well as to provide a tool to help either application porting or simultaneous development.

With those guidelines, computer engineering students can test and modify the software, simulating real environments and improving their competences, for example proposing new interfaces.

As future work we propose the inclusion of an in depth comparison using eligible metrics, as well as extensive questionnaires and test-involving users of both platforms, since either are driven by user centred design.

REFERENCES

- [1] Apple Inc. "Designing for iOS/iOS Human Interface Guidelines," [Online]. Available:<https://developer.apple.com/library/ios/documentation/UserExperience/Conceptual/MobileHIG/>.
- [2] S. Nedyalkova and J. Bernardino, "Open source capture and replay tools comparison". International C* Conference on Computer Science and Software Engineering, C3S2E '13, pages 117– 119, New York, NY, USA. ACM, 2013.
- [3] Google Inc, "Material design in the 2014 Google I/O app" [Online]. Available: <http://android-developers.blogspot.pt/2014/08/material-design-in-2014-google-io-app.html>.
- [4] Apple Inc. "Color and Typography" [Online]. Available: https://developer.apple.com/library/ios/documentation/UserExperience/Conceptual/MobileHIG/ColorImagesText.html#//apple_ref/doc/uid/TP40006556-CH58-SW1.
- [5] Google, "Support Library revisions," [Online]. Available: <http://developer.android.com/tools/support-library/index.html#revisions>.
- [6] S. Liao, Migrating to Swift from Android, Apress, 2014, pp. 47-167. Google, "Action Bar," Google, [Online]. Available: <http://developer.android.com/training/appbar/index.html>.
- [7] Ericsson, "Mobility Report," Ericsson, [Online]. Available: <http://www.ericsson.com/res/docs/2015/mobility-report/ericsson-mobility-report-nov-2015.pdf>.
- [8] R. Nurik e V. Persson, "Design from iOS to Android and Back," [Online]. Available: [https://design.google.com/articles/design-from-ios-to-android/..](https://design.google.com/articles/design-from-ios-to-android/)
- [9] Microsoft, "Platform," [Online]. Available: <https://xamarin.com/platform>.
- [10] Google, "Custom animations," [Online]. Available: <http://developer.android.com/training/material/animations.html#ViewState>.